

An Efficient Active and Reactive Power Control of DFIG for a Wind Power Generator

Sabah Louarem

Department of Electrical Engineering,
Laboratory DAC HR,
Ferhat Abbas University Setif 1, Algeria
slouarem@univ-setif.dz

Tarek Bouktir

Department of Electrical Engineering,
Ferhat Abbas University Setif 1,
Algeria
tbouktir@univ-setif.dz

Djamel Eddine Chouaib Belkhat

Department of Physics,
Laboratory DAC HR,
Ferhat Abbas University Setif 1, Algeria
djamel.belkhat@univ-setif.dz

Saad Belkhat

Department of Electrical Engineering,
Laboratory DAC HR,
Ferhat Abbas University Setif 1, Algeria
sbelkhat@univ-setif.dz

Abstract—During the last decade, wind energy gained much importance as an energy source in power systems. DFIG energy is one of the most widely accepted types of renewable energy generation because of its several benefits. This paper presents a comparative study on the performance of different control strategies for DFIG wind turbines: proportional-integral (PI), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), H_∞ , and adaptive Fuzzy PI controller. Simulation results show that DFIG's performance, dynamic response, and robustness against machine parameter variations are improved with H_∞ control technique.

Keywords—wind energy; DFIG; PI controller; ANN controller; H_∞ controller; adaptive fuzzy PI controller

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, severe environmental problems attracted the world's attention to renewable energy utilization [1]. Renewable energy sources, safe and reliable for the environment, are locally available energy sources [2]. Among them, wind power has received considerable attention [3]. Wind energy conversion systems (WECS) can be classified in two categories: variable and fixed-speed WECS. Among these techniques, variable speed wind generators are frequently used compared to fixed-speed systems because of their efficient energy production, improved power quality and dynamic performance during grid faults [4]. In this context, the doubly-fed induction generator (DFIG) has proved its worth as a powerful solution to improve the power rating of wind [4-5].

Several control algorithms have been proposed to improve DFIG-based wind turbine system's behavior during normal operation [6]. Most of these control laws were generally based on the vector control concept. For instance, decoupled control of active and reactive power in a DFIG-based wind energy conversion system with conventional PI controllers has been proposed in [7]. The main disadvantage of this kind of controllers is that they require accurate knowledge of

machine's parameters [8]. To address this issue, several studies focused on advanced and robust controllers have been conducted. For example, Predictive Functional Control (PFC) [9] was proposed in order to reduce the incidence of machine's parameter variations. In the same context, a predictive power controller synthesized by using a linearized state-space model of DFIG has been proposed in [10]. The design of an Adaptive Fuzzy Gain Scheduling of Proportional Integral controller (AFGPI) has been performed in [11] to address the issue of parameter changes and satisfactory power response was obtained, compared to the conventional PI controller. A neuronal controller has been designed in [12] to control the rotor currents of DFIG. The robustness of the proposed controller has been tested when the stator and the rotor self-inductances increased by 20%.

Another robust H_∞ control design, based on a vector control strategy, has been carried out in [13] for the purpose of controlling active and reactive power flow between DFIG and the grid. The tracking control performance of the proposed controller was evaluated by modifying the machine's parameters. The obtained simulation results were satisfactory, showing the robustness of the H_∞ compared to the conventional PI controller. Recently, a robust power command based on the Active Disturbance Rejection Control (ADRC) for DFIG used in a WECS system has been designed in [14]. Simulation results showed that the proposed ADRC controller had the best performance in terms of robustness against machine's parameter variations. In the DFIGs, the stator is directly connected to the grid and the rotor is connected to the grid via the machine's and grid's inverters.

In this paper, a comparative study of four kinds of controllers (PI, ANN, H_∞ and adaptive fuzzy PI controllers) is performed for the purpose of driving the power flowing between the stator of the DFIG and the grid.

II. MODELING OF THE WIND TURBINE CONVERSION SYSTEM

The diagram of the DFIG-based wind turbine is shown in Figure 1, where RSC and GSC are respectively the rotor side converter and the grid side converter.

Fig. 1. Basic configuration of a DFIG wind turbine

A. Wind Turbine Model

The fraction of power extracted from the wind by a wind turbine is usually referred by the symbol C_p , which stands for the coefficient of performance or power coefficient. The actual mechanical power output P_m of a wind turbine is given as [15-16]:

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot \pi \cdot R^2 C_p(\lambda, \beta) v_{wind}^3 \quad (1)$$

where, P_m is the mechanical output power of the turbine [W], ρ is the air density [Kg/m^3], R is the rotor radius [m], and β is the blade pitch angle [deg].

The power coefficient expresses the rotor aerodynamics as a function of both tip speed ratio λ and pitch angle of the rotor blades β . The tip speed ratio is defined as the ratio between the blade tip speed and the wind speed, expressed as [17]:

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega R}{v_{wind}} \quad (2)$$

where ω is the rotor speed [rad] and v_{wind} is the wind speed [m/s].

In order to determine C_p , the following generic equation is used [18-19]:

$$C_p = (0.5 - 0.0167 \cdot (\beta - 2)) \cdot \sin\left[\frac{\pi \cdot (\lambda + 0.1)}{18.5 - 0.3(\beta - 2)}\right] - 0.00184 \cdot (\lambda - 3) \cdot (\beta - 2) \quad (3)$$

B. Modeling of the Doubly-Fed Induction Generator

Concordia and Park's transformation will be applied to the three-phase model of the IG. Dynamic voltages equations in an arbitrary $d-q$ reference frame are following [20-21]. The stator voltage equations are:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{sd} &= R_s I_{sd} + \frac{d}{dt}(\varphi_{sd}) - \omega_s \varphi_{sq} \\ V_{sq} &= R_s I_{sq} + \frac{d}{dt}(\varphi_{sq}) - \omega_s \varphi_{sd} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The rotor voltage equations are

$$\begin{cases} V_{rd} = R_r I_{rd} + \frac{d}{dt}(\varphi_{rd}) - (\omega_s - \omega_r) \varphi_{rq} \\ V_{rq} = R_r I_{rq} + \frac{d}{dt}(\varphi_{rq}) - (\omega_s - \omega_r) \varphi_{rd} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The stator current of DFIG was decomposed into active and reactive component via the coordinate transformation and the field-oriented vector transformation. In order to regulate the power of the DFIG based wind turbine system, the vector control strategy is used. It consists of using the flux orientation, such as stator flux orientation (SFO) [7-22]: $V_{sd} = 0$ and $V_{sq} = V_s = \omega_s \varphi_s$. The active and reactive powers at the stator side and rotor side of the DFIG are given as:

$$\begin{cases} P_s = -V_s \frac{L_m}{L_s} I_{rq} \\ Q_s = \frac{V_s \psi_s}{L_s} - \frac{V_s L_m}{L_s} I_{rd} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{cases} V_{rd} = R_r \cdot I_{rd} + \left(L_r - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s}\right) \frac{dI_{rd}}{dt} - g\omega_s \left(L_r - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s}\right) I_{rq} \\ V_{rq} = R_r \cdot I_{rq} + \left(L_r - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s}\right) \frac{dI_{rq}}{dt} + g\omega_s \left(L_r - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s}\right) I_{rd} + g\omega_s \frac{L_m \cdot \varphi_s}{L_s} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

In steady state, the second derivative terms in (7) are neglected and the third term constitutes cross-coupling terms.

$$\begin{cases} V_{rd} = R_r \cdot I_{rd} - g\omega_s \left(L_r - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s}\right) I_{rq} \\ V_{rq} = R_r \cdot I_{rq} + g\omega_s \left(L_r - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s}\right) I_{rd} + g\omega_s \frac{L_m \cdot \varphi_s}{L_s} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

III. CONTROLLER SYNTHESIS

A. PI Controller Synthesis

Figure 2 shows the block diagram of the system controlled with the PI controller. The terms K_p and K_i represent the proportional and integral gain respectively. The ratio B/A represents the transfer function to be controlled, where A and B are presently defined as follows:

$$A = L_s R_r + p L_s \left(L_r - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s}\right) \text{ and } B = -L_m V_s \quad (9)$$

The response time of the controlled system will be fixed to 10ms. This value is sufficient for our application, while a lower value could involve transients with important overshoots. The calculated terms are given in [7-23].

Fig. 2. System with PI controller

The transfer function of the open loop becomes:

$$G(p) = -\frac{k_p \frac{L_m V_s}{L_r L_s - L_m^2}}{p} \quad (10)$$

The transfer function of the closed loop is expressed by:

$$H(p) = \frac{1}{1+p\tau_r} \quad (11)$$

where τ_r is the response time.

Now, we express the controller gains correction based on the settings of the machines and the response time as follows:

$$\begin{cases} k_p = -\frac{1}{\tau_r} \frac{L_s(L_r - \frac{L_m^2}{L_s})}{L_m V_s} \\ k_i = -\frac{1}{\tau_r} \frac{R_r L_s}{L_m V_s} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

B. ANN Controller Synthesis

ANN models are inspired from the basic framework of the brain [24-25]. In this study, the ANN controller was performed by using the nftool of Matlab. The DFIG-based wind turbine is simulated with the PI controller. The data, before and after the controller are computed and saved. After that, the network training was done for 10 iterations. The hidden layers contained 40 neurons.

Fig. 3. Neural network structure

C. Design of the H_∞ Controller

In this section, we present the H_∞ mixed-sensitivity synthesis method for robust tracking control design. The main idea consists of synthesizing the controller by minimizing H_∞ 's performance. As mentioned above, the quotient B/A represents the transfer function to be controlled. Thus, we can define the tracking error, the input control and the output as:

$$e(s) = S(s)Y_{ref}(s) \quad (13)$$

$$u(s) = K(s)S(s)Y_{ref}(s) \quad (14)$$

$$Y(s) = T(s)Y_{ref}(s) \quad (15)$$

where $S(s) = \left(I + \frac{B(s)}{A(s)} K(s) \right)^{-1}$ is the sensitivity function and $T(s) = \frac{B(s)}{A(s)} K(s) \left(I + \frac{B(s)}{A(s)} K(s) \right)^{-1}$ is the closed-loop transfer function. We are interested in designing the controller $K(s)$. For that, we will consider the H_∞ mixed-sensitivity design problem illustrated in Figure 4, where, $W_1(s)$ and $W_2(s)$ are selected as loop-shaping weights. Hence, the tracking control design is considered as an optimization problem which consists of finding a stabilizing controller $K(s)$ to minimize the following cost function:

$$\left\| \begin{bmatrix} W_1(s)S(s) \\ W_2(s)K(s)S(s) \end{bmatrix} \right\|_\infty \quad (16)$$

Fig. 4. S/KS mixed-sensitivity minimization

The design weights $W_1(s)$ and $W_2(s)$ were selected as:

$$W_1(s) = \frac{6000}{s+30} \quad (17)$$

$$W_2(s) = \frac{0.0025s^2}{0.0005s^2+5s+100} \quad (18)$$

By using the robust control toolbox of Matlab, we obtain the following controller:

$$K(s) = \frac{-2.98 \times 10^4 s^3 - 3.00 \times 10^8 s^2 - 2.7 \times 10^{10} s - 4.20 \times 10^{11}}{s^4 + 1.25 \times 10^6 s^3 + 1.23 \times 10^{10} s^2 + 6.19 \times 10^{11} s + 7.34 \times 10^{12}} \quad (19)$$

D. Adaptive Fuzzy PI Controller Synthesis

The adaptive fuzzy PI controller scheme is given in Figure 5. The FLS inputs are the errors (e) in active, reactive, and rate of change in active and reactive power error (de). The output of the fuzzy controller is du. In contrast to the controller where controller parameters (k_p and k_i gains) are tuned in a predefined way [30], FLS is used to tune the k_p and k_i parameters of the PI so that the controller can keep up with parametric changes and reference signals can be tracked.

Fig. 5. PI control system with fuzzy gain adapter

The fuzzy sets are defined as: NB is Negative Big, NM is Negative Medium, NS is Negative Small, ZR is Zero, PS is Positive Small, PM is Positive Medium, PB is Positive Big, B is Big and S is small. The max-min reasoning method and the center of gravity defuzzification method are used [31]. The values of K'_p and K'_i are determined by a set of fuzzy rules of the form designed fuzzy gain scheduling controller has two inputs and two outputs.

$$K'_p = \frac{K_p - K_{pmin}}{K_{pmax} - K_{pmin}} \quad (20)$$

$$K'_i = \frac{K_i - K_{imin}}{K_{imax} - K_{imin}} \quad (21)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Comparative simulations of the controllers were performed in Matlab. The proposed control algorithm's nominal parameters are indicated in the Appendix. It was first tested in ideal mode and driven to 1500rpm. The different controllers

were tested and compared by two different criteria, namely reference tracking performance, and robustness by varying the system parameters.

A. Reference Tracking in Ideal Conditions Mode

Simulation results of active and reactive power using the classical PI controller, an ANN controller, the proposed H_∞ controller and the proposed adaptive fuzzy PI controller are shown in Figure 6. As expected, both active and reactive powers have been produced with good accuracy. Moreover, they can track the desired reference after a finite time interval and the answers are without overshoots for different controllers.

Fig. 6. Active and reactive power behavior

Fig. 7. Zoom in active and reactive power behavior

Figure 7 shows a zoom view of active and reactive power behavior from 0 to 0.005s to compare the response times of all controllers. We can notice a quicker response time for ANN and H_∞ controllers. In the same context, we notice that the system controlled by the PI controller evolved to a steady state with an important response time in comparison with the other controllers.

Fig. 8. Evolution of cumulative tracking error functions

In order to show which controller has the best steady state accuracy, we graph the evolution of the following cumulative tracking error functions:

$$CTE_P = \int_0^t |P_s - P_{sref}| dt, \quad t \in [0 \ 2s] \quad (22)$$

$$CTE_Q = \int_0^t |Q_s - Q_{sref}| dt, \quad t \in [0 \ 2s] \quad (23)$$

As shown in Figure 8, the H_∞ controller has the best steady state accuracy in comparison with the other controllers. In contrast to the H_∞ controller, the conventional PI controller has low steady state accuracy.

B. Robustnes

We are interested in evaluating the robustness of the different controllers against parameter variation for parameters such as the inductances L_s, L_r , the mutual inductance L_m and the resistance R_r . The controllers' performances are compared according to rise time, maximum peak overshoot and settling time. We test the robustness of the controllers against mutual inductance variations. Figure 9 and Table I present the simulation results for a parametric variation in the order of -10%. Unlike the adaptive fuzzy PI controller and the H_∞ controller, we can remark that the ANN and PI controllers lose their performance regarding maximum overshoot.

Fig. 9. Active and reactive power behavior with -10% mutual inductance variation

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF THE RESPONSE PARAMETERS ($L_m - 10\%$)

Active power			
Controller	Rise time (s)	Maximum overshoot (%)	Settling time (s)
PI	0.0102	29.43	0.0541
ANN	0.0018	7.62	0.0023
H_∞	0.0023	0.77	0.001
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0024	0.01	0.0042
Reactive power			
PI	0.0102	19.20	0.0252
ANN	0.0005	7.62	0.0021
H_∞	0.0005	1.20	0.0010
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0024	0.14	0.0042

In order to refine our study, we tested the robustness of the proposed controllers against a mutual inductance variation in the order of -25%. The simulation results are presented in Figure 10 and Table II. We can note that the PI and ANN controllers lose their performance in response time with undesirable maximum overshoots and only adaptive fuzzy PI controller and H_∞ controller can resist this parametric variation with a slight superiority for H_∞ controller in terms of response time.

Fig. 10. Active and reactive power behavior using H_∞ and adaptive fuzzy PI controllers with -25% mutual inductance variation

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF THE RESPONSE PARAMETERS ($L_m - 25\%$)

Controller	Rise time (s)	Maximum overshoot (%)	Settling time (s)
Active power			
H_∞	0.0014	1.95	0.0057
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0060	0.61	0.0104
Reactive power			
H_∞	0.0015	2.96	0.0058
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0060	0.70	0.0106

In the same way, the robustness of the proposed controllers against rotor inductance variations was tested. Two deep simulations have been performed (Figures 11 and 12). The first one concerns a variation in the order of +10% and the second a variation in the order of +25%. The results are shown in Tables

III and IV respectively. Note that only two controllers have resisted the second test with slight superiority regarding response time for the H_∞ controller. Regarding stator inductance variations, the simulation results are shown in Tables V and VI. As in the preceding cases, only the H_∞ and the adaptive fuzzy PI controllers can resist the high stator inductance variation.

Fig. 11. Active and reactive power behavior with 10% rotor inductance variation

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF THE RESPONSE PARAMETERS ($L_r + 10\%$)

Active power			
Controller	Rise time (s)	Maximum overshoot (%)	Settling time (s)
PI	0.0066	11.94	0.0414
ANN	0.0011	0.37	0.0012
H_∞	0.0003	0.40	0.0005
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0013		0.0023
Reactive power			
PI	0.0060	17.76	0.0427
ANN	0.0003	17.16	0.0013
H_∞	0.0003	0.78	0.0005
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0013	0.25	0.0024

Fig. 12. Active and reactive power behavior using H_∞ and adaptive fuzzy PI controllers with +25% rotor inductance variation

TABLE IV. COMPARISON OF THE RESPONSE PARAMETERS ($L_r + 25\%$)

Controller	Rise time (s)	Maximum overshoot (%)	Settling time (s)
Active power			
H_∞	0.0007	0.93	0.0011
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0028	0.31	0.0106
Reactive power			
H_∞	0.0007	1.54	0.0038
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0028	0.18	0.0011

Fig. 13. Active and reactive power behavior using the four controllers with +10% variation of L_s

TABLE V. COMPARISON OF THE RESPONSE PARAMETERS ($L_s + 10\%$)

Active power			
Controller	Rise time (s)	Maximum overshoot (%)	Settling time (s)
PI	0.0066	11.51	0.0411
ANN	0.0010	0.36	0.0012
H_∞	0.0003	0.39	0.0005
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0024	0.01	0.0042
Reactive power			
PI	0.0068	17.11	0.0424
ANN	0.0003	18.86	0.0012
H_∞	0.0003	0.74	0.0005
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0013	/	0.0023

TABLE VI. COMPARISON OF THE RESPONSE PARAMETERS ($L_s + 25\%$)

Controller	Rise time (s)	Maximum overshoot (%)	Settling time (s)
Active power			
H_∞	0.0007	0.90	0.0011
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0028	0.01	0.0049
Reactive power			
H_∞	0.0007	1.30	0.0011
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0003	1.80	0.0052

Finally, regarding the rotor resistance variation, which is the result of the rotor heating, a deep simulation was performed by considering a rotor resistance variation in the order of 100%. The simulation results are shown in Figure 15 and

the controllers' performances are summarized in Table VII. Thus, we can see that the different controllers can drive the system to track the reference signals. In other words, the active and reactive powers follow correctly the reference signals.

Fig. 14. Active and reactive power behavior using the H_∞ and adaptive fuzzy PI controller with +25% variation of L_s .

TABLE VII. COMPARISON OF THE RESPONSE PARAMETERS ($R_r + 100\%$)

Active power			
Controller	Rise time (s)	Maximum overshoot (%)	Settling time (s)
PI	0.00220	1.17	0.02330
ANN	0.00020	0.10	0.00020
H_∞	0.00003	0.39	0.00007
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.0002	/	0.00050
Reactive power			
PI	0.00240	5.15	0.1500
ANN	0.00005	24.37	0.1498
H_∞	0.00001	71.37	0.1499
Adaptive Fuzzy PI	0.00004	3.01	0.1500

As far as the active power is concerned, it is clear that the H_∞ controller has the best rise time and settling time when compared with the other controllers. However, concerning reactive power, the controller performances are almost identical to those of the ANN controller with a slight superiority for H_∞ controller. In a nutshell, the simulation results presented in this work have shown that the H_∞ controller has the best steady state accuracy compared with the other controllers. Regarding the robustness against parametric variation, the H_∞ and adaptive fuzzy PI controllers have the best tracking performance and robustness with a slight superiority of the H_∞ controller.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the control of doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) based wind energy conversion has been studied. The DFIG's stator was directly connected to the grid and the rotor was connected to the grid via the machine's and grid's inverters. The design of four control strategies, namely PI, ANN, adaptive fuzzy PI, and H_∞ controller, has been presented and discussed. The

obtained results showed that the H_{∞} controller is the best to drive the DFIG's stator and to track perfectly the active and reactive power references with very good tracking performance, namely low-rise time, low settling time, and high steady-state accuracy. The H_{∞} controller seems more robust than all other controllers against parameter variations.

Fig. 15. Active and reactive power behavior using the four controllers with +100% variation of R_r .

APPENDIX

Rating of the wind turbine	
Power	$P=1.5MW$
Radius	$R=35.5m$
Inertia	$J=1000Kg.m^2$
Gear box ratio	90
Damping coefficient	$f=0.0024Nm.rad^{-1}$
Wound rotor induction machine	
Power	1.5MW
Stator voltage	$V_s=398/690V$
Rotor voltage	$V_r=225V$
p	2
Wind turbine parameters	
Blades radius	$R=35.25m$
Gain of gearbox	$G=90$
Air density	$\rho=1.225kg/m^3$

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